

D6.3 Ethics Management Plan

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Ethics Advisor

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
CAA Denmark	Danish Civil Aviation Authority
CARE	Collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics
CBEM	Community-based Environmental Monitoring
CMLO	Coastal Marine Litter Observatory
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DFG	German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
Dx.x	Deliverable number
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
ECACC	European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures
EMP	Ethics Management Plan
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
EU GA	EU Grant Agreement
EU-PolarNet	Integrated European Polar Research Programme
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FPIC	Free prior informed consent
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IASSA	International Arctic Social Sciences Association
ICAA	Icelandic Civil Aviation Administration

ICC	Inuit Circumpolar Council
ICETRA	Icelandic Transport Authority
PCBs	Polychlorinated Biphenyls
PFAS	Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PMG	Project Management Group
POPs	Persistent Organic Pollutants
OCPs	Organochlorine Pesticides
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
RiS	Research in Svalbard
UNDRIP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples
WPx	Work package number

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document is the Ethics Management Plan (EMP) of the ICEBERG project (project number 101135130), which is produced in month 9 (M9) of the project. This deliverable addresses the requirements for ethics and research integrity of Horizon Europe as described in Article 14 (section: Ethics) in the Grant Agreement (EU GA). This deliverable is associated with the D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) and the D6.2 First Data Management Plan (DMP) and will later be accompanied by the Mid-term Data Management Plan (D6.4) in M18 and the Final Data Management Plan (D6.5) in M36.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of the EMP is to address ethical concerns - related to human participation, artificial intelligence (AI), and organic and inorganic samples - that arise during the project's life cycle. The ethics of human participation will discuss more in depth the procedures related to informed consent and participation requirements, including how vulnerable groups and Indigenous knowledge will be addressed during the project. The EMP will explore how AI will be used in the ICEBERG project and how all risks involved with AI will be identified and mitigated. The EMP will also address the different protocols, permissions and documentation required in obtaining, handling and transporting biological and non-living samples.

1.3 EMP Methodology

The EMP was developed by UOULU in collaboration with UFZ and ICEBERG's Ethics Advisor, Laura Puumala, and Data Protection Steward of UOULU under the Task 6.4 Data management and ethics (UOULU). UOULU and UFZ collected data from all partners regarding data management and ethics (rules and regulations, working with humans, working with organic and inorganic samples, and AI). The responses have been compiled and presented in this EMP. The EMP defines the project's ethical principles to be respected for the duration of the ICEBERG project.

1.4 Ethical governance procedures

Of the 16 consortium partners, six institutions have an ethics committee. In addition, two institutions are in the process of setting up an ethics committee and one institution has an internal research board. Some institutions also have legal departments and data protection officers that ensure compliance with personal data protection.

The following ethical governance procedures will be followed:

- CAU Kiel Guidelines for good scientific practice
- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
- Ethics for researchers- Facilitating Research Excellence in FP7
- Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK guidelines 2019)
- French Office for Research Integrity (Ofis) guidelines
- High Council for Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (Hcéres) guidelines
- Rules for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice at the UFZ

- Svalbard Environmental Protection Act
- University of Aegean ethical regulations (followed by SCI as a spinoff company)
- University of Akureyri Code of Ethics
- Ilisimatusarfik's guidelines for ethical research (2024)

In addition, the ICEBERG project met with Arctic Hub in Greenland (<https://arctichub.gl/>) and is featured on the Arctic Hub Connect Map that displays research projects in Greenland.

1.5 Ethical considerations

The following are ethics and legal issues that could have an impact on data sharing in the ICEBERG project:

- The project involves research with Indigenous and non-Indigenous individuals and communities. It engages with adults, youth, and elders. The project must consider how to share data with local communities and Indigenous communities, and how to ensure that the data benefits them. See Sections 3.1 Indigenous and traditional knowledge and 3.2 Vulnerable groups
- Recruitment of participants among field site communities must take into consideration inclusiveness and aim for diverse representation regarding gender, identity, social-cultural and socio-economic factors. However, participant selection is limited to those that can give informed consent.
- In case of the possibility for unexpected findings in the results or in the engagement with the informants, they will be handled according to the established procedures at each organisation, referring participants beforehand to the relevant support services. In the case of Greenland, ethical procedures will be elaborated and will take into account the ongoing process in Greenland to establish ethical guidelines for research with Greenlandic communities.

As per the ICEBERG Description of the Action (DoA) Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, possible ethical issues will be minimised by:

- Developing ethical principles that will be implemented in the research process such as the principle to let participants have their name shown in the data as a knowledge holder if they wish, and so, aiming to better respect Indigenous perspectives and Indigenous rights.
- Only collecting data that is necessary for the research context.
- Ensuring that no personal data is to be transferred between partners in different countries.

2 Informed consent and personal data

2.1 Informed consent

All study participants will be asked for their written informed consent in paper or electronic format for taking part in the study (participation or audio/visual recording) and for data processing before the start of an interview, focus group, or a survey. Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in the participant information sheet that accompanies the consent form dealing with personal data.

Voluntariness and informed consent will be ensured by:

- Plain language written consent forms and participant information sheets will be provided, as well as oral explanations of the purpose and format of obtaining data.
- Clear explanation will be provided on all parts of the consent form prior to any interview or stakeholder engagement, with opportunities for participants to ask questions.
- The researcher will provide honest and thorough answers for any questions asked about the consent form or research.
- During the consent process, each researcher will ensure that the information is fully comprehended by the individuals being interviewed, thereby allowing for an informed decision to be made.
- Ensure that the individual understands that they can withdraw from the study at any time and voice any criticism, disappointment or negative feedback to the interviewer without penalty or repercussions.
- The consent form will also include an option for the participant to request a copy of the document prior to publication, and to receive acknowledgment/recognition.
- Participants who wish to be named when quoted will be provided a chance to review the quote(s) they have provided prior to publication to double check that their knowledge is well represented and correctly understood by the researchers.
- The researcher will document the consent process by keeping detailed records of all discussions, questions asked, and the individual's consent (in field notebooks).
- The consent form outlines how data will be processed, stored, used, and potentially re-used. It will also include the contact details of the project coordinators to facilitate participants' questions, requests, and possible withdrawal.

Each participant will be provided with a comprehensive Information Sheet (see Section 8) detailing the purpose, scope, and methodology of the research, along with any potential risks and benefits involved. Participants will also receive a Consent Form (see Section 8), which they will review and sign along with the signature of the researcher(s) before engaging in any study-related activities. This form will outline their rights, including the option to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence, ensuring that informed and voluntary participation is maintained throughout the research process. The two documents are written in clear, accessible language to foster transparency and understanding. The two documents can be provided in English, Danish, Icelandic, Norwegian and Greenlandic.

2.2 Personal data

As per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, personal data will be treated according to personal data processing legislation – The General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and local personal data protection regulations in EU and non-EU/EEA partner countries. See DMP Section 6.2 for relevant data

protection regulations followed by the ICEBERG project. No personal data is to be transferred between partners in different countries. Only anonymised or aggregated data will be shared with partners. Personal research data will be destroyed after the end of the research project.

The DESCA ICEBERG Consortium Agreement Attachment 6 defines the roles of data controller and data processor. As per these definitions, the data controllers will typically be the partner institutes, while the data processors will depend on the methods used to collect or generate data. ICEBERG partner institutes are the data controllers bound by data control laws and regulations while those bound by data processing laws and regulations can be both ICEBERG partners and third parties if/when third parties somehow use or process the ICEBERG data. For example, if using a survey method, the data processor would be the third-party survey platform (e.g. LimeSurvey GmbH). For interview methodology, the data processors may be the partner institutes themselves (unless a third-party service is used, for example a professional transcription service). In the case that a third party is used to process data, a data processing agreement according to Article 28 GDPR (Processor) is in place.

Personal data processed in the ICEBERG project are:

- Data collected in the Informed Consent form (names and postal address or electronic address in case participants wish to receive the results of the research)
- Signed consent forms
- Gender, age (the participants will include people aged over 18 years of age with the exception of 16-year-old students)
- Main occupation (e.g. for interviews with stakeholders and political actors)
- Area of living (region/city/area code)
- Photographs and video materials (e.g. from art-based methods)

Sensitive personal data concerning mostly indirect health related (not medical data), racial, or ethnicity data gathered from the interviews and focus groups will be processed in the study. Sensitive data is processed on the legal basis of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, as outlined in Article 9(2) of the GDPR. In the case of, for example, interviews where sensitive data is shared, the sensitive information provided is done so voluntarily by the participants and therefore, participants willingly give informed consent to the study.

ICEBERG does not specifically ask questions about sensitive information. Confidential and the most sensitive information about Indigenous participant's relationship with the ocean and the land will not be shared (such as spiritually important sites).

3 Human participation

3.1 Indigenous and traditional knowledge

It is important to be aware that data in the project generated as a result of working with Indigenous communities may be subject to different or additional ethical considerations. Science in modern terms is often associated with western thinking based on a Eurocentric knowledge system (Aikenhead and Ogawa, 2007) and its attempts to incorporate Indigenous knowledge may be seen as a form of colonialism (Liboiron, 2021). A point of difference between these knowledge systems is that traditional knowledge is often about “ways of knowing, not what is known” and thus does not generate data (footnote 46/p. 53, Liboiron, 2021). Given the distinct nature between traditional ways of knowing and dominant science’s methodologies, the project needs to consider how to implement data principles that are tailored with indigenous rights in mind.

One such guideline is the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (<https://www.gida-global.org/care>): Data principles created to advance the legal principles underlying collective and individual data rights in the context of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). CARE is distinctly separate from FAIR in that FAIR principles focus on increased data sharing alone, while CARE principles encourage data sharing in both a people-oriented and purpose-oriented way (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). Without the consideration of people, data sharing alone creates tension for Indigenous Peoples and ignores power differentials and historical contexts (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). The CARE Principles are (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, 2022):

- **Collective Benefit:** Data ecosystems shall be designed and function in ways that enable Indigenous Peoples to derive benefit from the data.
- **Authority to Control:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and interests in Indigenous data must be recognized and their authority to control such data respected.
- **Responsibility:** Those working with Indigenous data have a responsibility to share how those data are used to support Indigenous Peoples’ self-determination and collective benefit.
- **Ethics:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages of the data life cycle and across the data ecosystem.

Regarding the last principle of ethics, as per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, the project will follow the ethical and methodological guidelines of the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA, 2020), and in Greenland also the Ilisimatusarfik’s guidelines for ethical research (2024) and the Inuit Circumpolar Council’s (ICC) protocols on Ethical and Equitable Engagement (ICC, 2022). These principles include:

- Responding to and supporting local communities’ needs with the research and knowledge co-produced. During consultation meetings, attending community members have highlighted a list of priority issues of concerns that ICEBERG research should address.
- Respecting and including Indigenous ways of knowing: ICEBERG includes Indigenous methodologies such as storytelling, community gathering, etc.
- Respecting free, prior and informed consent (FPIC), a principle that is included in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

Stakeholder engagement will follow the recommendations of:

- Integrated European Polar Research Programme (EU-PolarNet 2020)
- EU-PolarNet White paper on stakeholder engagement in polar research (Latola et al., 2020)
- A toolkit for Community Based Participatory Research in Greenland (Rink and Reimer, 2019)

The recommendations of the above resources highlight the importance of adopting a high degree of coordination among different activities to avoid stakeholders' "research fatigue" while optimising efforts. Other recommendations include trust building and early engagement, proper allocation of time and funding, diversity and equity in the engagement process, seeking for participation and collaboration, and careful and coordinated identification of stakeholder contact points (i.e. intermediaries). Building on these existing guidelines and protocols, ICEBERG will co-develop and implement an ethics evaluation framework, which will be presented in D4.1 Co-creation / citizen science framework and lessons learned. The ethics evaluation framework has the purpose of continuously evaluating the ICEBERG consortium's engagement with research ethics throughout the duration of the project. Central to this framework are 'points of co-evaluation' over the project's lifetime. 'Points of co-evaluation' are spaces and moments of engagements where different actors, such as consortium members and project partners, can come together and reflect on the ethical dimension of their work. Based on the ICEBERG project's progress and the needs of the different people involved, the ethics evaluation framework is being adapted accordingly.

In addition, the ICEBERG Code of Conduct (D4.2) is a framework for self-regulation that includes practices for research collaboration with Indigenous communities.

3.2 Vulnerable groups

Citizen science is an important part of the ICEBERG project. Since participant selection among the three field site communities takes into consideration inclusiveness and aims for diverse representation, there is also a possibility that vulnerable group members will take part in the research, including people with disabilities, people facing socio-economic challenges, the elderly, and pregnant women. The participation of any vulnerable people will be based on the ability to nonetheless give informed consent.

The project will not involve individuals under 18 years of age, with the exception of 16-year-old students who are part of a class where the teacher operates a drone for marine litter mapping. The group of students will engage in a research-related activity under the strict supervision of both the teacher and the responsible partners, ensuring full compliance with ethical guidelines and obtaining the necessary consents. Having these youth participants do not lead to any additional ethical risks or worries.

In the South-West Greenland field site, ICEBERG project members will engage with the communities of Narsaq, Qaqortoq and Nanortalik. Working in a predominantly Indigenous context, the ICEBERG project follows the Ilisimatusarfik's guidelines for ethical research (2024).

The table below presents potential risks to vulnerable groups and mitigation strategies to minimise these risks.

Table 1. Potential risks to vulnerable groups and how to mitigate them.

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
Recalling traumatic events in relation to environmental disturbances including pollution triggered by some of the questions	Right to withdraw at any time. If wished, interviews can be carried out with the presence of a person who has the trust of the community and can intervene with culturally appropriate ways
Concern of findings disrupting traditional way of life or producing	Co-creation methodologies, research transparency of project goals, and open discourse about findings.

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
negative results about their community	
Concerns that time and contributions of participants will not be adequately compensated	Mechanisms in place for non-monetary and monetary formats for compensation of research participants. E.g. participation prizes and opportunity to have one's name shown as a knowledge holder.
Misrepresentation of information expressed in interviews through the analysis of a researcher	Presenting/sharing research findings with interviewees who indicated in the consent form the wish to receive the results prior to publication, and giving them the opportunity to input, suggest or amend before publication. Double-checking knowledge provided non-anonymously will be practiced.
Concerns may arise that a focus group participant will worry about information shared during the session being disclosed by others outside the group.	Focus group rules emphasizing confidentiality will be established. Participants will be asked to keep information confidential, and open communication will be encouraged throughout the session to ensure participants feel safe discussing their concerns.

The project also aims to ensure data sharing with local communities and Indigenous rights holders, and to ensure that data or the knowledge built on the collected data benefit them. Below are the strategies that will be employed by the project:

- Regular workshops and meetings with community members for feedback and to share findings
- Communities' wishes, needs and preferences will be discussed during the community consultation meetings (what research questions are relevant to different community members) in the three field sites
- Local representatives in project advisory board and feedback/evaluation meetings with advisory members throughout project process every six months
- Local pollution mitigation strategies co-produced and shared with communities
- Involvement of locals as co-authors of publications and as co-presenters at conferences if wished and if budget allows
- A joint presentation at classes at the high school at Qaqortoq (Greenland), at the University of Akureyri, at the Húsavík Knowledge Centre (Iceland) and at the University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS) (Svalbard)
- Participatory feedback sessions on the CBEM platform: Communities' wishes, needs, and preferences will be discussed
- Photographs and data will go through a local curator (training workshops provided)
- Care is taken to communicate in the language of the case study regions through translation of materials and hiring local interpreters

4 Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning

The ICEBERG project involves machine learning and AI in several methodologies. Consortium partner, SciDrones (SCI) has created the Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO), which uses unmanned aerial systems and machine learning algorithms to automatically detect and map marine litter in coastal zones. Time-lapse cameras installed by Kiel University (CAU) will also develop a machine learning approach to analyse time-series data of field-based cameras. For modelling results with pathways and impact of pollutants in seawater, Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research (GEOMAR) may use AI for analyses of model results and for coding scripts for analysing model results.

As a quality assurance for AI data, human oversight is required for data validation and monitoring. For AI activities used for detecting litter on collected drone images, developers and deployers are involved in the process of training, monitoring and validating AI therefore maintaining human agency and oversight requirements. Information about the employed AI methods is publicly available on the CMLO platform website (<https://cmlo.aegean.gr/>). SCI will self-assess the trustworthiness of their AI by undertaking the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI). Confidence level on AI decisions is also provided. For the time-lapse images and time-series datasets, these will be analysed by machine learning approaches, but there will still be human oversight to help ensure that the results derived from the data are accurate. Students and teachers ("the citizens") will actively participate in developing the application for the time-lapse cameras. They will receive training in image analysis and image categorization, such as identifying types of marine litter. Humans (including local community members) perform quality checks on the cameras to ensure that the time-series data used for analysis is of high quality, accurate, and reliable.

To ensure data protection for drone images, a quality check will be conducted to identify any images that unintentionally capture individuals. While the AI does not collect, store or process personal data, it may happen that people are unintentionally captured in images during flight missions. SCI will take actions to protect anonymity by blurring or/and deleting those parts of the images. Time-lapse data will be stored and processed according to the principles of the EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users (https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/privacyhandbook_en.pdf). CAU is supported by CAU Research Data Management to ensure data protection, fairness, and non-discrimination (<https://www.datamanagement.uni-kiel.de/en>).

The following guidelines for data collection and handling will be followed:

- Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
- Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence
- Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)
- ESA (European Space Agency) Corporate Social Responsibility Code of Conduct
- EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users
- EU Commission - Ethics for researchers

4.1 Time-lapse Cameras

4.1.1 Iceland

Certain sections of the littoral zone in Iceland are privately owned and permits from landowners (farmers) have been requested and granted. For other areas, the municipality of Húsavík has been contacted, and the application is currently pending at the time of writing the EMP. An information letter written in Icelandic and English is attached to the cameras to inform people walking by about the project and the use of the cameras.

4.1.2 Greenland

Time-lapse cameras will be installed within the area of the municipality of Qaqortoq. CAU members are in the process of applying for the permits from the municipality. An information letter written in Greenlandic and Danish will be attached to the cameras to inform people walking by about the project and the use of the cameras.

4.1.3 Svalbard

The ICEBERG research project has been registered in the Research in Svalbard (RiS) portal. Time-lapse camera installation method has been approved by the Governor to minimize environmental risk and/or cultural damage (e.g. guy ropes are banned as they pose a risk of wildlife entanglement).

4.2 Drones

In the ICEBERG project, the drone model used is the DJI Mavic 3 Enterprise. It is a professional-grade drone designed for industrial applications, featuring a high-resolution camera, and advanced RTK positioning for precision mapping and inspection tasks. It offers enhanced flight performance, extended battery life, and robust data security, making it ideal for surveying and mapping operations. The DJI Mavic 3 Enterprise falls under the C1 category of drones, with a take-off weight of approximately 920 grammes.

The use of drones in Iceland and Greenland is subject to strict regulations aimed at ensuring safe, responsible, and ethical operations. Adherence to these regulations is essential to uphold privacy, environmental protection, and safety, especially when drones are used for research, commercial, or personal purposes. This section outlines the regulatory framework and ethical considerations for drone use in both Iceland and Greenland, including the specific rules and obligations for operators.

4.2.1 Iceland

As a member of the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), Iceland follows EASA's harmonized regulations for the operation of drones. In addition, Iceland also has regulations that are country specific. Therefore, the key legal and ethical considerations for drone operators in Iceland, must reflect both EASA guidelines and local regulations enforced by the Icelandic Transport Authority (ICETRA). Drone operations within the ICEBERG project fall under the Open category under EASA.

Responsible partners will follow the following key regulatory and ethical considerations:

- Registering the drone with the Icelandic Civil Aviation Administration (ICAA) as the drone weighs more than 250 grammes, and will have an ID attached to it,
- Obtaining a license as the drone weighs more than 250 grammes,
- Flying below 120 metres above ground level to avoid conflicts with manned aircraft,
- No flights within 2 kilometres from any international airports and 1,5 kilometres of any other airports,
- No flights within 50 metres of any building in urban areas and 150 metres in rural areas.
- Protecting wildlife by following environmental guidelines when flying the drone nearby sensitive wildlife areas.

4.2.2 Greenland

Drone regulations in Greenland are specific due to Greenland’s status outside the EU. Both the Danish Civil Aviation Authority (CAA Denmark) and the Greenlandic Transport Authority are involved in regulating drone operations in Greenland, but the primary authority is CAA Denmark. The Greenlandic Transport Authority addresses more localized concerns within Greenland, especially regarding environmental protection and specific local restrictions. Specific ethical considerations apply due to Greenland’s unique environment and cultural heritage.

EASA licenses (from the EU) are not recognized in Greenland, meaning that responsible partners need additional permits from the Greenlandic local authorities. Partners will comply with Greenland’s national legislation, as outlined in BL 9-4 under the Danish Air Navigation Act including the following rules:

- Drones must stay at least 5 km from public aerodromes and 8 km from military airbases,
- The minimum distance from built-up areas and major public roads is 150 m,
- Drones must not fly higher than 100 m above the ground,
- Flights will not take place over the three sensitive nature reserves in Greenland (the National Park of Greenland, Melville Bay and Angujaartorfiup Nunaa, southwest of Kangerlussuaq) that are referred to in BL 7-16.

Additionally, responsible partners will not film or pursue polar bears, as stipulated in §4, 4 of Executive Order No. 3 of 14 September 2018. Ethical operation in Greenland involves strict adherence to these rules to protect both human safety and wildlife.

4.3 Impacts of using drones and time-lapse cameras

Along with the intended use of AI and capturing plastic pollution in images for the ICEBERG project, there is also the possibility for unintentional outcomes. Therefore, the ICEBERG project has identified the potential negative social and environmental impacts of using AI and compiled the table below to discuss how to minimise these impacts.

Table 2. Potential negative impacts of use and handline drones, time-lapse cameras and how to minimize them

Potential negative social and/or environmental impacts	Plans to minimize negative impacts
Time lapse cameras are powered by batteries that may pose a potential risk to the environment if not handled properly	To ensure safety, caution is being exercised to protect the batteries from any external damage. The batteries are secured in a waterproof, hard plastic box to protect them from external factors such as animals and water. This box is fastened to a tripod leg using weatherproof adhesive tape and a tensioning strap, positioned approx. 20 - 30 cm above the ground. The tripod itself is anchored to the ground with a tensioning strap and an anchoring system. With these precautions, we reduced the risk of battery displacement or loss.

Potential negative social and/or environmental impacts	Plans to minimize negative impacts
<p>Images of humans could be unintentionally captured during the usage of drones and time-lapse cameras</p>	<p>Drones: Following Iceland’s privacy laws, we will not capture images or videos with people. However, if unforeseen images containing people do occur, project members responsible for this process will Ensure anonymity by blurring or deleting such parts of drone-captured images.</p> <p>Time-lapse cameras: Given the automatic nature of the time-lapse approach, manually blurring specific parts of images is impractical. With 15 cameras capturing one image per hour over three years, reviewing all images manually is not manageable. Instead, blurring/deleting parts of the images will be applied only to training and validation data. The final application will operate automatically, with no risk posed by individuals accidentally appearing in images. Output maps will focus solely on litter (raw data will not be shared).</p>
<p>Injury or property damage/ damage to landscapes or wildlife</p>	<p>Drones: Efficient and detailed training for participants, routine maintenance and recovery of drones if such event happens.</p> <p>Time-lapse cameras: to prevent potential harm to animals, researchers avoid using sharp or mesh components, such as nets. There are also no fine cords or small parts that could entangle animals or be ingested by them. The connecting cable between camera and external batteries is securely fastened to a tripod leg with weatherproof adhesive tape and cable ties to ensure that it does not hang loose.</p>

5 Organic and inorganic samples

ICEBERG project researchers will strive to collect organic and inorganic samples from the local environment and ecosystems in a low-impact way to avoid potential risks. Organic samples in ICEBERG are materials derived from living organisms, such as plants, animals, and bacteria. Inorganic samples collected and used in ICEBERG are derived from sediments, snow, ice, and water. Standard protocols for collecting organic samples, which adhere to international guidelines, include preparation, site selection, proper sample collection, post-collection care, detailed documentation, appropriate storage and transport. Biological material transfer documents may be required for the transportation of samples between countries.

5.1 Sediment sampling

- **Svalbard:** All soil and marine sediment sampling plans are reported to the Governor of Svalbard in keeping with applicable deadlines. Sampling activities are carried out in accordance with Svalbard Environmental Protection Act and, in the case of sampling within protected areas (such as South Spitsbergen National Park), on the basis of relevant permits issued by the Governor of Svalbard.
- **Iceland:** soil sampling will happen in state-owned territories in 2025. No permit is needed.
- **Greenland:** a permit for collection and export of sediments including soil will be applied for from the Government of Greenland, Mineral Resources Authority for the field work season 2025.

5.2 Food samples

Samples of food items representative of local diets, mainly of animal origin (seafood, birds and mammals), will be collected in local stores, from professional fishermen or by a veterinarian in abattoirs, and transported for analysis. The specific matrices and the required number of samples of each matrice will be decided upon evaluation of the dietary habits of the target populations. With this aim, an anonymous survey will be distributed among voluntary participants (both in paper and electronically) by local members of the ICEBERG project. Cod liver, haddock liver, arctic char, fish fillet, shark meat lamb meat, guillemot or berries are among the expected matrices to be analysed due to their frequency of consumption and/or the bioaccumulation of contaminants. After reception to the ONIRIS laboratory, these samples will be properly stored until analysis by chromatographic techniques couples to mass spectrometry. The analytical scope will cover the most relevant persistent organic pollutants (POPs), including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), dioxins/furans, and per- or polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). Additionally, suspect screening will be performed on selected samples to assess the presence of additional chemical contaminants of interest. All the analyses will be performed using methods accredited under the ISO17025 regulations in a National Reference Laboratory for the targeted analytes. Samples will remain stored until the end of the project and will be destroyed afterwards according to the current regulation. In Greenland, an application will be submitted to the Ethical Committee for health research.

5.3 Analysis of contaminants on the quality of human breast milk

Samples of breast milk will be collected from voluntary donors in compliance with the requirements of the UNEP Guidelines for Organization, Sampling and Analysis of Human Milk on Persistent Organic Pollutants ([UNEP Guidance HumanMilk 2017 En.pdf](#)). The storage, treatment, analysis and disposal of breast milk samples will be performed in the same way as food samples (see section 5.2), using adapted methodologies

for this specific matrix under the ISO17025 regulation in the NRL. No personal information about the donors will be gathered in any case.

The Directorate of Health in Iceland will be contacted in due time. An application will be submitted to the Ethical Committee for health research in Greenland.

5.4 Toxicological impact analysis of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) on human digestive health

The work on in vitro human cells will be performed in WP2 using commercially available human cell lines. To this end, ICEBERG considers intestinal cell co-culture models, simulating the epithelium-mucus axis in the human upper and lower gastro-intestinal tract (Caco-2/HT29-MTX and T84/LS174T, respectively) and HepaRG cell line, known to exhibit many characteristics similar to primary human hepatocytes. The impact on several biological processes (e.g. cell viability, barrier function, inflammatory response, genotoxicity, oxidative stress, activation of nuclear receptors) will be assessed.

Cell derivatives will be stored until a maximum of two years after the end of the project, after which they will be discarded. All information is property of the provider (European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC) or Biopredic) and non-disclosed to the owner, with exception of the information that is publicly disclosed by means of websites (<https://www.culturecollections.org.uk/>, <https://wepredic.com/en/biopredic>).

The following guidelines will be followed for data collection and handling:

- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- Nagoya Protocol (2010)
- Research in Svalbard (RiS) guidelines

5.5 Impacts of working with organic and inorganic samples

Potential risks associated with organic and inorganic samples are described in Table 3.

Table 3. Potential risks to local environment/ecosystem and humans and how to mitigate the risks

Potential risks to local environment and ecosystems	Mitigation strategy
Damage or disturbance (e.g. to plants) caused by sample collection	Careful selection of sampling locations and reducing sample sizes to the necessary minimum. In the case of soil sampling, backfilling sampling spots.
Polluting sampling area with mismanaged sampling equipment (e.g. filters, vials, nets) or chemicals (e.g. acids)	Adjusting sampling procedures to Arctic conditions to eliminate or reduce equipment loss and contamination risk
Failure to respect donor consent and anonymity	The informed consent form will be completed by donors in accordance with the UNEP guidelines

Potential risks to local environment and ecosystems	Mitigation strategy
	(UNEP Guidance HumanMilk 2017 En.pdf) ; Donor anonymity will be ensured by a process of anonymization and coding of samples

6 Conclusions

This Ethics Management Plan presents the ethical requirements, principles, and guidelines to be followed during the entire scope of the ICEBERG project. As a multidisciplinary project, ICEBERG will be involved in various types of studies involving human participation, AI, and organic/inorganic sample collections. Therefore, this EMP ensures compliance with EU/national, legal, and ethical requirements in the countries where the project's activities are carried out. This document is an addition to the ICEBERG Code of Conduct (D4.2) which is a framework for self-regulation that includes practices for internal and external research collaboration framed through the concepts of fairness, respect, care, and honesty. The ICEBERG consortium is understanding of how essential good ethics practices are in research and is committed to follow and respect all requirements set out in this EMP.

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8 Appendix

This section displays two appendices:

- an example participant information form used in the ICEBERG project,
- an example consent form for participants used in the ICEBERG project.

INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS – ICEBERG Project

Researchers: Thora M. Herrmann, Élise Lépy, Luisa Lollo – University of Oulu, Finland
 Joan Nymand Larsen, Jón Haukur Ingimundarson, Þórný Barðadóttir – Stefansson Arctic Institute, Iceland
 Ilona Mettiäinen, Adam Stepien, Pamela Lesser, Katharina Heinrich – Lapland University, Arctic Centre, Finland
 Anne Chahine, Nina Döring – Helmholtz Centre Potsdam-GFZ, Germany
 Tahnee Prior – Women of the Arctic, Finland
 Christine Liang – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research-UFZ, Germany
 Annegret Kuhn, Natascha Oppelt, Victor Lion – Kiel University, Germany
 Apostolos Papakonstantinou, Argyris Moustakas – SciDrones P.C., Greece
 Muriel Bonin-Mercier – INRAE, France
 Gaud Dervilly – ONIRIS, France

The ICEBERG research project (2024-2026) is funded by the European Union.

You are invited to participate in a research project. Before accepting, please take the time to read this document which presents the conditions of participation. Do not hesitate to ask any questions that you may have to the person who presents this document.

Research objectives

The ICEBERG project studies ocean and coastal pollution and creates governance and resilience strategies with Arctic communities in Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland), Iceland and Svalbard. The ICEBERG project has 3 goals:

- 1) to study the sources, types and spread of ocean and coastal pollution - like plastics, ship emissions, wastewater - from long-distance transport via the open ocean and atmosphere or from regional sources such as industry and from thawing glaciers, snow, and ice;
- 2) to assess the effects of pollution on the environment and on people and communities;
- 3) to co-design strategies with communities to reduce pollution (mitigation), make communities less vulnerable to pollution (adaptation), and develop policy recommendations for pollution-control governance.

Your participation in the research

Your participation in this research includes a semi-structured interview or focus group to discuss your observations and experiences with pollution and environmental changes, and their effects on local practices, food security, well-being, health, identity, and infrastructure. We will also discuss how regulations influence pollution in your area and how pollution impacts different groups such as women, men, elders, youth. Additionally, we will discuss how communities and researchers collaborate. The interview or focus group will include a participatory interactive or paper mapping activity, allowing you to highlight areas of concern regarding environmental disturbances. The interview will last 30-45 minutes, and the focus group about an hour. With your permission, the interview will be audio-recorded to facilitate transcription. The time and place will be arranged according to your preferences.

You are invited to join a year-round citizen science activity to detect and map coastal marine litter using drones and time-lapse cameras. We will provide training in drone operation, camera setup, data collection, and analysis, including identifying and categorizing marine litter. You can suggest key beach areas to monitor, assist with camera setup and check-ups, and conduct drone flights to track litter. The data will help create maps of hotspot areas for targeted environmental interventions like clean-ups. The citizen science activities are separate from interviews and focus groups, and will take place during the participants own time and depending on their own activity. Your participation in the citizen science activities is entirely optional. If you choose not to participate in the interviews and/or focus groups, you can still fully engage in the citizen science activities.

Benefits, risks or possible disadvantages of your participation

There is no particular risk in participating in this projects. It is possible that there are no direct benefits of participating in this study for you particularly, but the mitigation, adaptation and governance strategies developed during this study may benefit your area in the future. Participating in this research gives you an opportunity to share and discuss confidentially your personal observations and experiences of pollution, environmental changes and disturbances, including how they affect local nature and practices, food, health, identity, as well as the impact of regulations and policies on pollution in your area. It is possible that telling your story gives rise to moving or uncomfortable thoughts or memories. If this happens, do not hesitate to talk to the person conducting the interview. Confidential and the most sensitive information about your relationship with ocean and the land will not be shared (such as spiritually important sites).

Compensation

Travel costs due to your participation in this research will be compensated. Participating in this research will not incur any extra costs on you. If you would like to read the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the project, we can send them to you upon request.

Voluntary participation and right of withdraw

Your participation in the ICEBERG project is entirely voluntary. You can terminate your participation and withdraw your already given consent at any time without negative consequences or prejudice and without having to justify your decision. If you decide to end your participation, it is important to inform the researchers whose contact details are included in this document. Upon withdrawing your consent to participate all personal information about you will be destroyed. However, the research data collected so far may be used in the research.

Privacy and data management - Personal data included in the research materials

In this research, personal data like name, signature, contact information, age, occupation, gender, voice (if audio recorded) will be collected through interviews, focus groups, and maps.

Lawful basis of processing this personal data is Article 6(1) of the EU General Data Protection Regulation citing scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes. Sensitive personal data concerning most indirectly health related (not medical data) and racial or ethnic origin gathered from the interviews and focus groups will be processed in the study. Sensitive data is processed on the legal basis of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, as outlined in Article 9(2) of the General Data Protection Regulation.

Your personal data is confidential. The following steps will be taken to ensure the confidentiality of the information provided by you:

- Your name will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication. A code will be assigned to each interviewee and only the researchers will know his/her/they identity. Only this code will appear in scientific publications. Only if you wish your name to be cited in recognition of your role as knowledge holder, knowledge bearer of nature-related knowledge in the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the ICEBERG project, we will mention your name.
- We will record the interview only with your agreement.
- Personal data processed in IT systems: i) username ; ii) password. Processing of direct identifiers: i) direct identifiers will be removed in the analysis phase
- The research material will be archived without identifiers. The material will be archived for 10 years at each participating research organization. Only the research team has access to the data and only for scientific analysis.
- Research materials, including data and records, will be kept in a secure location. Recordings will be transcribed and the transcripts will be destroyed, along with any personal information, 10 years after the project ends. Only non-identifying data will be retained after this period.
- No personal data will be transferred or disclosed to recipients outside the research group.
- The University of Oulu, Finland is leader of this research project. Consortium members mentioned above have all access to the data for non-commercial, scientific purpose only. Data transfers to Iceland are based on the adequacy decision made by the EU.

Rights and Exceptions

- You have the right to obtain information on whether or not personal data concerning you are being processed in the project, as well as the data being processed. You can also request a copy of the personal data undergoing processing (GDPR Article 15). If there are inaccuracies or errors in your personal data undergoing processing, you have the right to request their rectification or supplementation (GDPR Article 16).
- You can request the erasure of your personal data on the grounds specified in GDPR Article 17 on Right to erasure and you can limit the processing of your personal data for reasons cited in GDPR Article 18 on Right to restriction of processing.
- You can request to receive the personal data you have submitted to the Universities (GDPR Article 20).
You have the right to object to processing your personal data. The University will no longer have the right to process your personal data unless it can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds for the processing that override the interests, rights and freedoms of the data subject, or unless it is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defense of legal claims. The University can continue processing your personal data also when necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of the public interest (GDPR Article 21).
- In certain individual cases, derogations from the rights described above in this section “Your rights as a data subject”, and exceptions to these rights may be made on the basis of the GDPR and the Finnish Data Protection Act, insofar as the rights render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes. The need for derogations will always be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

Data Controller: University of Oulu, Pentti Kaiterankatu 1, P. O. Box 8000, 90014 OULU, Contact of Data Protection Officer: dpo@oulu.fi.
If you have any questions about data privacy issues, or the rights of participants, or wish to withdraw from the research, **you can contact the ICEBERG project coordinating team: Thora Herrmann, thora.herrmann@oulu.fi, ph: +49 173 1985 042; Élise Lépy, elise.lepy@oulu.fi**

Complaints or Criticism

You have the right to lodge a complaint with the Data Protection Ombudsman’s Office if you think your personal data has been processed in violation of applicable data protection laws.

Contact details: Data Protection Ombudsman’s Office (Tietosuojavaltuutetun toimisto)

Street address: Lintulahdenkuja 4, 00530 Helsinki Postal address: PL 800, 00531 Helsinki, Finland

Switchboard: +358 29 566 6700 Registry: +358 29 566 6768 E-mail: tietosuoja@om.fi

PARTICIPANT WRITTEN CONSENT FORM – ICEBERG Project

Declaration of Consent

- I understand that I can take my time to think before agreeing or not to participate in the research project.
- I can ask questions to the research team and demand satisfactory answers.
- I understand that by participating in this research project, I am not relieving researchers of their responsibilities.
- I understand that my name will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication. Only, if I wish my name to be cited in recognition of my role as knowledge holder, knowledge bearer of environmental-related knowledge in the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the ICEBERG project, my name will be mentioned.
 - Yes, I like my name to be cited.
- I authorize the researchers to audio-record the interview. Yes No
- I authorize the researchers to distribute the photographic material that I have provided to them, knowing that the material will be accompanied by a credit to the author of the work (respect of copyright) and only used for non-commercial, scientific purpose.
- I have understood that my participation in this research is voluntary and that I may, whenever, announce that I will no longer participate in it. In such case the research data collected so far may be used for the research.
- I have received sufficiently information regarding the research and any questions have been answered. I have understood the information that has been given to me and I wish to participate in the research. I have read the Privacy Notice regarding this research

Signatures

I, the undersigned _____ give my freely given and informed consent to participate in the ICEBERG research project. I read the *Information For Participants* regarding this research project and understood the purpose, nature, advantages, risks and disadvantages of the project. I am satisfied with the explanations, clarifications and answers that the researcher has provided me, if any, regarding my participation in this project.

Signature of the participant

Date and Place

A brief summary of the research results will be sent to participants who request it. Please provide the address where you would like to receive the document. Results will not be available until 2026. If this address changes before then, please inform the researcher of the new address to ensure you receive the summary.

The address (e-mail or postal) to which I would like to receive a short summary of the research results is:

I explained the purpose, nature, benefits, risks and disadvantages of the research project to the participant. I answered the questions to the best of my knowledge and checked the participant's understanding.

Signature of the researcher

Date and Place

Additional Information

If you have any questions or wish to withdraw from the research, please contact the ICEBERG project coordinating team: Thora Herrmann, thora.herrmann@oulu.fi, ph.+49 173-1985-042 or Élise Lépy, elise.lepy@oulu.fi

This document has been made in duplicate, one for the research participant and one for the researcher.